

Effect of seedling age on yield components of T. aman rice varieties.^a BRRRI, Joydebpur, Bangladesh, 1988.

Seedling age (d)	BR11	BR22	BR23	Nizersail
<i>Tillers (no./m²) or 25 DT</i>				
30	205 a	221 a	194a	259 a
45	207 a	150b	180a	279 a
60	187 a	135b	99 b	255 a
<i>Panicles (no./m²) at harvest</i>				
30	216 a	246 a	191 b	308 a
45	238 a	230 ab	205 b	308 a
60	219 a	206 b	236 b	310 a
<i>Flowering (DT)</i>				
30	65	56	60	55
45	67	55	58	55
60	67	53	57	53
<i>Duration (DT)</i>				
30	94	87	89	84
45	93	85	88	82
60	93	83	86	81
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>				
30	3.1 a	3.0 a	3.8 a	2.9 a
45	2.5 a	3.1 a	4.1 a	3.2 a
60	2.6 a	3.4 a	2.3 b	2.8 a

^a In a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 1% level. DT = days after transplanting.

varieties are recommended for areas where planting 45 d after sowing cannot be guaranteed. ■

Effect of summer plowing on N volatilization and rice yield in sandy loam soils

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Farmers in Thanjavur district think summer plowing results in poor establishment of rice seedlings, loss of soil N (by volatilization), and loss of yield.

We studied the effect of summer plowing on yield in a split-plot design on sandy loam "New Delta" soil of Cauvery Delta. Treatments were four tillage methods and three levels of N (see table).

N volatilization in all plots was monitored for 24 d. Volatilization from summer-plowed plots (141 g/ha per d) was 4 times higher than from conventionally plowed plots (32 g/ha per d).

Seedling establishment and water requirement did not vary appreciably among tillage treatments (see table).

Grain yield averaged over all N treatments was not significantly affected by tillage, but increased as N increased from 100 to 150 kg N/ha. This response was greatest (about 2 t/ha) with summer plowing and no puddling. All treatments

that involved puddling gave similar yields and similar responses to N.

We conclude that when at least 150 kg N/ha is applied, summer plowing (with or without puddling) can be recommended for the sandy loam soils of Cauvery Delta. ■

Effect of tillage on seedling establishment, water requirement, and grain yield of rice. Thanjavur, India.

Tillage method	Seedlings established (no./m ²)	Water requirement (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha) at N level of			Mean yield (t/ha)
			100 kg/ha	125 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	
Conventional puddling (without summer plowing)	62	648	5.5	5.8	6.4	5.9
Summer plowing without puddling	58	634	4.7	5.8	6.7	5.7
Summer plowing with one puddling at planting	64	602	5.2	5.7	6.4	5.8
Summer plowing with two puddlings at planting	60	584	5.5	6.3	6.5	6.1
Mean	-	-	5.2	5.9	6.5	5.9
LSD	N level	-	0.2			
	Between 2 tillage practices at any one level of N		0.5			
	Between 2 levels of N at any one tillage practice		0.5			

Integrated pest management – diseases

Natural infection of rice yellow mottle virus disease (RYMV) on rice in Sierra Leone

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Occurrences of RYMV in Sierra Leone have increased, particularly in the lowlands. We studied the effect of natural infection on rice variety IR65 in our associated mangrove swamp at Rokupr in the northwest.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 5-m² plots with 20 cm between rows and 10 cm between hills, with three replications.

Effect of RYMV on IR65. Rokupr, Sierra Leone, 1989 wet season.

Hill	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Panicles (no./hill)	Empty spikelets (%)	Discolored grains (%)	Yield (g/hill)	Yield reduction (%)
Healthy	83.0	9	7	11	17	9.4	
Infected	69.3	13	9	83	87	1.6	82
LSD (0.05)	8.3	3.6	ns	12	8.3	2.7	

Fertilizer was applied at 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha, using urea, single super-phosphate, and muriate of potash. P was applied basally; N and K were applied in three equal splits at early tillering, maximum tillering, and panicle initiation.

Severe mottling and stunting occurred in two plots; the third plot had healthy plants with no apparent symptoms.

We examined 25 hills randomly selected from each plot.

Natural infection by RYMV disease resulted in 17% stunting, 72% increase in spikelet sterility, 66% increase in grain discoloration, and 82% reduction in yield (see table). Viral infection increased tiller production but did not significantly affect number of panicles/hill. ■